

Close-to-Community Provider Motivational Indicator Scale

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in terms of how you *typically* feel in your current work as a close-to-community care provider. **Please answer every question by filling the appropriate circle ○, not leaving any blank.**

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
	1	2	3	4	5
1. I am satisfied that I accomplish something worthwhile with my work	○	○	○	○	○
2. I am satisfied with the positive impact of my work	○	○	○	○	○
3. I am satisfied with the support I receive from my colleagues	○	○	○	○	○
4. I am satisfied with the community thanks and recognition I receive for my work	○	○	○	○	○
5. I am proud to be working for my organization as a CTC provider	○	○	○	○	○
6. My organization really inspires me to do the very best on the job	○	○	○	○	○
7. I am proud to be working for my community	○	○	○	○	○
8. My community inspires me to do the very best I can for them	○	○	○	○	○
9. I can be relied upon at work	○	○	○	○	○
10. I always complete my tasks efficiently and correctly	○	○	○	○	○
11. I take initiatives to do things without being asked or told	○	○	○	○	○
12. I am a hard worker	○	○	○	○	○

Instructions: Given the multi-dimensional component of the scale, it is recommended that scores on each of the sub-scales are calculated separately for each of the four dimensions, either as a total sub-scale score or as a mean sub-scale score for use in subsequent analysis.

The subscales present in the **CTC Provider Motivational Indicator Scale** are as follows:

- Satisfaction at Work – Items 1 - 4
- Organizational Commitment – Items 5 - 6
- Community Commitment – Items 7 - 8
- Work Conscientiousness – Items 9 -12

Alternatively, and given that the results of the four-factor latent structure supports the idea that the sum value approximates the true value of the latent variable, a **motivation indicator score** can also be quickly and easily obtained by calculating a sum total score of all 12 items.

Suggested Citation: Vallières, F., Kok, M., Mahmud, I., Sarker, M., Jeacocke, P., Karuga, R., Limato, L., Kea, A.Z., Chikaphupha, K., Sidat, M., Gilmore, B. and Taegtmeier, M. (2020). Measuring motivation among close-to-community health workers: developing the CTC Provider Motivational Indicator Scale across six countries. *Human Resources for Health* **18**, 54. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12960-020-00495-7>.